

Tau-philic light new physics at Belle-II

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Abstract

New physics scenarios addressing the flavor puzzle generally predict dominant interactions with fermions of the third generation. In this talk, I will discuss the prospects for probing light particles beyond the standard model — such as light vectors, scalars and axion-like particles — which possess dominant couplings to the tau lepton. In particular, I will focus on the possibility to investigate these scenarios at Belle-II. I will highlight the complementarity in direct searches, such as the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-\gamma\gamma$, $\tau^+\tau^-\gamma$, 3γ , mono- γ processes, and indirect probes, such as the impact of these new physics candidates on the τ anomalous magnetic and electric dipole moments. The correlated effects in these searches can offer unique hints at the underlying new physics dynamics and point at viable strategies that can be adopted to discriminate between different scenarios.

1 Introduction

The τ sector plays a role of paramount importance in the search for physics beyond the Standard Model (BSM), as accessing precise information about the tau lepton properties would translate to gaining knowledge on the flavor and CP structure of new physics (NP). The latter can be obtained by comparing different leptonic observables over the three generation of leptons, such as, for instance, the electric (d_ℓ) and magnetic (a_ℓ) dipole moments for each lepton species ℓ [1]. A further theoretical motivation towards the study of the τ sector comes from well-motivated NP scenarios addressing the flavor puzzle which generally predict larger couplings to the third generation of fermions [2–13]. With this respect, a considerable effort has been put in constraining such kinds of NP scenarios under the assumptions of heavy new states, appearing at energy scales larger than the electroweak one ($m_{\text{NP}}^2 \gg v$), both within an effective field theory (EFT) approach, or in the framework of specific UV completions of the standard model (SM). Less attention has been paid to the possibility to explore tau-philic light new physics candidates, i.e. NP states that couple mainly to the third generation of leptons and which possess masses significantly lower than the electroweak scale ($m_{\text{NP}}^2 \ll v$). Despite the ever-increasing attention that light NP states have been receiving over the last decade as possible probes of new BSM symmetries, their relation to τ physics is still relatively unexplored.

In this paper I will discuss some recent developments in this direction, with a focus on the complementarity between direct and indirect searches for new light tau-philic states at Belle-II. In particular, I will first discuss the possibility to probe light NP indirectly, by studying the impact it has on the τ electric and magnetic dipole moments [14, 15]. In the second part, I will rather discuss complementary direct searches to probe light tau-philic NP [15, 16]. In tackling both of these problems, I will adopt an EFT approach, by parameterizing in the most general way possible the $U(1)_{\text{em}}$ -invariant interactions of new SM singlet states with τ_s and photons.

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This approach is well justified at the typical energy scales available at Belle-II ($\sqrt{s_B} \simeq 10 \text{ GeV} \ll v$), where the effects of weak interactions can be safely neglected, in a first approximation, as they are expected to yield corrections at most of order $s_B/m_W^2 \simeq 2\%$. Furthermore, such a generic parameterization allows to capture the main phenomenological features of a wide variety of specific UV complete models.

More into details, in the following, I will adopt the parameterization in [15] and describe the interactions of a new generic spin-0 state ϕ with τ leptons and photons as follows,

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi^{\text{int}} = \phi \frac{m_\tau}{\Lambda} \bar{\tau} (c_S^\tau + ic_P^\tau \gamma_5) \tau + c_{\gamma\gamma} \frac{\alpha_{\text{em}}}{4\pi} \frac{\phi}{\Lambda} F^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\nu} + \tilde{c}_{\gamma\gamma} \frac{\alpha_{\text{em}}}{4\pi} \frac{\phi}{\Lambda} F^{\mu\nu} \tilde{F}_{\mu\nu}, \quad (1)$$

where $F_{\mu\nu}$ is the electromagnetic field-strength tensor and $\tilde{F}_{\mu\nu} = 1/2 \epsilon_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} F^{\rho\sigma}$ its dual. The interactions of a new generic spin-1 state X that I will consider are instead given by the following dimension-4 operators:

$$\mathcal{L}_X^{\text{int}} = ig_D X_\mu \bar{\tau} \gamma^\mu (c_V + c_A \gamma_5) \tau + g_D e^2 C_A \epsilon^{\mu\nu\alpha\beta} X_\mu A_\nu \partial_\alpha A_\beta. \quad (2)$$

For further information on the choices adopted in these Lagrangians, I refer the reader to [15,16].

2 Indirect searches: τ dipole moments

The first probe of light tau-philic scenarios I will consider is given by the τ dipole moments. Due to the short lifetime of the τ lepton, the latter cannot be measured by studying the behavior of a τ in an external electromagnetic field, as it is the case for the lighter leptons. Several intense research programs are active in devising new experiments and techniques to measure a_τ and d_τ precisely, see, for instance, Refs. [17–29], as well as the recent measurements in peripheral Pb–Pb collisions at LHC [30–32]. A particularly appealing possibility is the one proposed in [33–36]. These works suggest to consider suitably constructed asymmetries in the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ process to access information on the momentum-dependent form factors $F_i(q^2)$ parameterizing the model-independent electromagnetic $\tau\tau\gamma$ vertex:

$$\langle \ell(p') | j_{\text{em}}^\mu | \ell(p) \rangle = e \bar{u}(p') \left[\gamma^\mu F_1 + (iF_2 + F_3 \gamma_5) \frac{\sigma^{\mu\nu} q_\nu}{2m_\ell} + (q^2 \gamma^\mu - q^\mu \not{q}) \gamma_5 F_A \right] u(p), \quad (3)$$

where $q = p' - p$ is the momentum of the virtual photon. From the aforementioned asymmetries, one can access experimental information on the form factors $F_2(s)$ and $F_3(s)$ at the operational Belle-II energy s . The τ dipole moments correspond to the zero-momentum counterparts of these form factors, $a_\tau \propto F_2(0)$ and $d_\tau \propto F_3(0)$, so that bounds on possible NP effects from such observables can be drawn only after performing a proper subtraction of momentum-dependent corrections [36,37]. These can in principle consist both of SM contributions and of BSM contributions. Indeed, in the presence of NP, one can generally parameterize form factors as consisting of a SM component and of a NP one:

$$F_{2,3}(s) = F_{2,3}^{\text{SM}}(s) + F_{2,3}^{\text{NP}}(s). \quad (4)$$

If NP is heavy ($m_{\text{NP}}^2 \gg s$), its contributions to form factors are real and simply result in modifications to the τ dipole moments, $F_2^{\text{NP}}(s/m_{\text{NP}}^2 \ll 1) \simeq a_\tau^{\text{NP}}$ and $F_3^{\text{NP}}(s/m_{\text{NP}}^2 \ll 1) \simeq 2m_\tau/e d_\tau^{\text{NP}}$. Therefore, in the case of heavy NP, one has to construct asymmetries that isolate the real part of form factors, $\text{Re} F_{2,3}$. These asymmetries necessarily require polarized electron beams, which will become available only with the Chiral Belle upgrade.

On the other hand, if NP is light ($m_{\text{NP}}^2 \ll s$), the relation between form factors and dipole moments becomes more involved. In fact, the real part of form factors cannot be directly related to the corresponding dipole moment, and one must pay attention to properly subtract the momentum-dependent NP contributions to form factors before drawing any conclusion on

Figure 1: Comparison of the sensitivity of the Belle II experiments to light NP affecting a_τ for $\Lambda = 1\text{TeV}$. *Left (Right)*: Bounds obtained assuming a sensitivity on $\text{Re}F_2^{\text{eff}}(\text{Im}F_2^{\text{eff}}) = 10^{-6}$ as a function of the mass of the NP mediator. See [14] for further details.

the corresponding dipole moments. In addition, as long as the photon momentum q exceeds in magnitude the pair production threshold for any pair of virtual particles, $q^2 > (m_i + m_j)^2$, form factors necessarily develop an imaginary part $\text{Im}F_{2,3}$.

Rather than being a hindrance, these features can be actually exploited in searches for light NP states [14, 15]. Indeed, whereas accessing the real part of form factors necessarily requires polarized electron beams, their imaginary part can be accessed already with the current setup of the Belle-II experiment. Form factors can then be related to the corresponding dipole moment provided that the momentum-dependence of the one-loop contribution is under control, as they both depend on the same NP couplings. Starting from the Lagrangian densities in Eq.(1) and (2), these contributions have been computed in [15] and result in the bounds displayed in Fig. 1. As it can be appreciated from such plots, measurements of the imaginary part of form factors would allow to place competitive limits in a wide region of the parameter space, before sensitivity is lost in the large mass limit, as expected from EFT decoupling arguments [14].

A second possibility that can be exploited in the case of light new physics is related to the threshold enhancements that form factors experience in the proximity of $s = 4m_\tau^2$. These energies can be obtained by either tuning the beam energy to the desired value, or by making use of radiative return techniques. While the former is unlikely to happen, the latter could be employed at Belle-II with the current setup, obviously at the price of some loss in statistics. If this is not too large, a measurement of $\text{Re}F_{2,3}$ at threshold energies would have the potential to place the most competitive bounds for the cases under consideration.

3 Direct searches

The same combination of Wilson coefficients that is responsible for generating the contributions to the τ dipole moments I have discussed in the previous section can be probed in complementary processes at colliders.

The most relevant direct searches to be considered for the light NP classes of models in Eq. (1) have been extensively studied in [16]. There, the authors investigated the processes at Belle-II that would allow to place the best bounds on scenarios involving a light tau-philic spin-0 state. Among these are the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-\gamma\gamma, \tau^+\tau^-\gamma, 3\gamma, \text{mono-}\gamma$ processes. The reach of such searches is summarized in Fig. 2, where also the bounds from τ dipole moments is reported. It is interesting to notice the high degree of complementarity between direct searches and indirect probes. While the former generally provide better constraints, the latter cover the whole mass range, while offering competitive benchmarks. In addition to this, it is interesting to observe that the search $e^+e^- \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-\gamma\gamma$ can in principle place the best bounds in a wide

Figure 2: Experimental exclusion bounds on tauphilic ALP (*left*), pseudoscalar (*center*), and scalar (*right*), as per Ref. [16] (to which we refer for a definition of the Lagrangian densities). The exclusion bounds from the imaginary part of the form factor F_2 are new; they are obtained assuming a sensitivity to the latter at a level of 10^{-6} , as for the real part.

Figure 3: Exclusion bounds from Belle II on a purely tau-philic light vector boson. *Left/Right*: Purely axial/vectorial couplings.

region of the parameter space. The search has not been performed yet at Belle-II, and would configure itself as a bump-hunt search in the invariant mass of the di-photon state, assuming that the latter is produced via the resonant decay of a light spin-0 mediator.

The Belle-II phenomenology of a light tau-philic vector boson X has been investigated into some detail in [15]. In particular, there it was suggested for the first time to probe such kind of scenarios by exploiting the anomalous Chern-Simons coupling $X\gamma\gamma$ in the processes $e^+e^- \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-\gamma$ and $e^+e^- \rightarrow \gamma + \text{inv}$, depending on whether the resonantly produced X decays visibly or invisibly. The analysis was performed for general axial and vectorial couplings, but can be specified to any model of interest. In particular, it is interesting to notice that the process $e^+e^- \rightarrow \gamma + \text{inv}$ can be employed to probe the scenarios proposed in [38] as a possible explanation to the $B \rightarrow K^{(*)}E_{\text{miss}}$ excess at Belle-II.

4 Conclusions

In this contribution I have discussed some appealing search strategies to probe light tau-philic NP scenarios at Belle-II. These include both direct and indirect searches. Among the former, I have stressed the potential reach of a search for light spin-0 states in the scattering process $e^+e^- \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-\gamma\gamma$. Regarding tau-philic light spin-1 states, searches based on processes mediated by the Chern-Simons $X\gamma\gamma$ coupling are particularly promising. As far as indirect searches are concerned, I outlined a strategy to probe the impact that BSM physics has on the τ dipole moments. This proceeds through measuring properly defined asymmetries in the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ process. For heavy NP, polarized electron beams are required in order to measure the desired asymmetries. In the case of light NP, however, a measurement of the normal asymmetry at Belle-II with the current experimental setup would suffice to bound the imaginary part of the form factor F_2 , which in turn translates to bounds on the Wilson coefficients of NP Lagrangians.

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